

Completing the Kandolo bathymetry with optimization

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Abstract—The Kasai River, affluent of Congo River, is one of the main transport axes for the Democratic Republic of the Congo. Many areas are clear of obstacle and are suitable for navigation but some channels like the Kandolo one are more difficult to cross. Due to its length of more than 2°153 km, it is difficult to achieve an accurate bathymetric survey over its entire length and in particular between small islands and in the vegetation zones. It is then proposed to complete the lack of bathymetric data in the Kandolo pass by using optimization and by coupling Telemac with OpenTURNS.

This application require first to construct a model using available bathymetric data and create patches zones in the area where bathymetric data is not available, mainly in the small passes between the two mains arms. On each of these areas, a bathymetric mesh gradient coefficient is built and will be used multiply by an optimization parameter to modify the bathymetry for each simulation run. A score is then calculate for each run by comparing the flows rates measured in situ on different profiles to the model results. Between each run, OpenTURNS is used to determine a new optimization parameter per area based on the previous score obtained.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Congo River, with 4700 km, is the second longest river in Africa after the Nile. It is the second largest in the world after the Amazon in terms of flow and watershed and irrigates the second largest tropical rainforest in the world. Moreover, due to its central position near the equator, with 1/3 of the river basin is in the northern hemisphere and 2/3 in the southern hemisphere, the river's flow is stable and the river is therefore navigable all the year and in all seasons.

These particularities make it possible to easily understand the tremendous opportunity represented by the development of river navigation on the Congo and its tributaries. However, the presence of natural obstacles does not allow continuous navigation over the whole area.

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II. THE PROJECT

A. The global project –Navigation Congo and Kasai River

ARTELIA has two ongoing studies on this project for the navigability of the Congo River. The first study consists in redefining a zero of navigation on all the waterways of the Congo and Kasai rivers. This zero of navigation will then make it possible to define the draught required for a defined vessel gauge.

B. The Kandolo pass

In parallel to this overall project, two rocky passes are being studied in more detail. This article refers to the study of the Kandolo Pass Fig. 1, 2 on the Kasai River. The results of the study will make it possible to:

- determine the hydraulic constraints at the passes;
- to analyse the ability of vessels to pass through the passes;
- map the shipping route.

C. Short presentation of OpenTURNS

Telemac2D is a software that allows to solve both river and marine free surface flows [1]. OpenTURNS is an uncertainty quantification tool or library that can easily be coupled with other software [2], [3]. It is funding by Airbus Group, EDF R&D, IMACS, ONERA, and Phimeca Engineering and distributed under the Lesser General Public License.

Fig 1 - Kandolo pass pictures

Fig 2 - Kandolo pass model and data

The coupling between the two tools has already been carried out on different studies, for erosion problems [4], [5] or better definition of parameters [6]. The use done here is relatively similar, with the reconstruction of a bathymetry that allows approaching as well as possible the distribution of the measured flows.

III. PROBLEMATIC

A. Available Data

The construction of the Digital Terrain Model (DTM) is based on three different sources of topo-bathymetric data. Two bathymetric surveys were conducted by boat on the study area, the first with the construction of transverse profiles on the main arms of the Kasai river, and the second with a higher density of points at the navigation channel of the Kandolo rocky pass. These bathymetric data are supplemented by lidar measurements of the area to obtain elevation in the out-of-water zones, ie on the islands and on the bank levels. All of these data are reported in Fig. 3. Several areas do not include information for the realization of the DTM mainly around the islands and at the level of the connections between the two main arms (the lidar data allow, however, to obtain an estimate of the water level in these zones). There are several reasons for the difficulty of obtaining information in these areas. On one hand the Kasai River is poorly developed in this zone with significant vegetation (Fig. 4) making the bathymetric measurements difficult. On the other hand, the lidar measurements and bathymetry were not performed at the same time and an area that could be emerged at the time of the bathymetric measurements by boat could be immersed at the time of the lidar survey.

Added to these data, in-situ flow measurements have been realized to obtain both an input flow for the model, as well as the flow in the main arms of the river which will be used to calibrate and optimize the model.

Fig 3 - Bathymetric and topographic data available in the area

Fig 4 - Vegetation in the Kandolo pass

B. Bathymetry reconstruction

Some areas of bathymetry not covered by the measurements can be estimated by extrapolation between existing data, such as the area without data further west. However, in the areas between the islands (between the 5 islets in the west and between the two main islands) the terrain model is more difficult to extrapolate, the missing areas may be at the same level as the surrounding bathymetry, deeper by phenomena of erosions, or near the level of the surrounding islands or in intermediate states. Although these data-free zones are outside the navigation channels, they can play an important role in the distribution of flows between the different arms of the river, as well as in speed throughout the model. It is therefore necessary to obtain an estimate of these funds to obtain a flow distribution close to the measurements.

IV. APPLICATION

A. Method

To obtain an estimate of the bottom elevation in these areas, an optimization method is used by performing several simulations and comparing model results with flow measurements. Between each simulation, bottom is changed in unknown areas. Given the large number of meshes (50000 for the entire model and over 3000 in areas without

bathymetry), it would be too expensive in computing time to vary the depth of each mesh node one by one, and so they have been grouped into 4 areas A, B, C, D (Fig. 5).

For each of these areas, it is necessary to build an initial bathymetry from the data, a coefficient field, and a parameter per zone, which will serve as variable parameters to optimize the bottom elevation according to the results. The final bathymetry is thus obtained from the following formula:

$$B_{final} = B_{initial} + F_A * P_A + F_B * P_B + F_C * P_C + F_D * P_D$$

with B_{final} the final bathymetry, $B_{initial}$ the initial bathymetry, F_i the field of zone i and P_i the variable parameters associated with each zone.

B. Initial bathymetry in unknown areas

Several methods can be envisaged to reconstruct the initial bathymetry of the optimization model in the unknown areas, either by interpolating between all the available data, or by performing a linear interpolation taking into account only the bathymetric files without the lidar, these zones being immersed. This second option was preferred to allow to build the coefficient fields in each zone more simply and to allow flow in the small arms between the two main arms.

C. Coefficient Fields

Given the initialization method chosen, the coefficient fields were constructed realizing a terrain model taking into account only the lidar (emerged) data, subtracting the initial bathymetry of the model, and keeping only the areas where there was no data, Fig. 6. With this construction, if we add the coefficient fields to the initial elevation we obtain the maximum elevation possible in the unknowns' areas.

D. Optimization parameters, coupling with OpenTURNS

Each field is associated with a parameter that will be optimized by OpenTURNS based on the differences obtained between the in-situ flow measurements and the flow computed by the hydraulic model.

Fig 5 - Area A, B, C and D defined in the model

The possible values of these 4 parameters (one per zone) depend on the way in which the previous steps were carried out. For our case, the maximum value is set to 1 for each fields, which corresponds to the elevation taking into account only the lidar data. The minimal value could be infinite but has been limited to -1, the bottom having little chance of being deeper.

The coupling with OpenTURNS is realized using a python script outside Telemac where before each simulation the 4 parameters P_i will be defined; and will be updated in Telemac. At the beginning of the Telemac calculation, the new bathymetry will be calculated into CORFON subroutine taking into account the parameters P_i , the fields F_i , as well as the initial bathymetry. The hydraulic model is then run until convergence. Then the flows are calculated with a python script and compared to the in-situ measurements to compute the error and transmitted to OpenTURNS to determine new parameters P_i .

The optimization loop is summarize on the Fig 7.

Numerous other methods can be considered to obtain an estimate of the missing bathymetry, for example to construct a gradient field as a function of the distance to the nearest available data or a combination of the two approaches. These approaches have not been evaluated at this time.

At this time, no optimization is performed on the friction coefficient. A Nikuradse length of 1 mm is set in area without lidar data and 1 cm in area with lidar data but these areas stay mainly over the water level for all the simulation with the inlet flow rate tested.

Three optimizations algorithms have been tested with closed results: the Multi-Level Single-Linkage (MLSL), the Dividing RECTangles and the Augmented Lagrangian algorithm.

V. RESULTS

86 simulations have been done until a minimal value on the flow rate error is obtained (at this time, only a high stopping tolerance of 10^{-5} has been tested). The Root Mean Square Error calculate over 7 flow rates with the python script evolve from $250 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ with the initial bathymetry to $98 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ with the final optimize bathymetry with a global flowrate imposed at the upstream boundary of the model of $5300 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The main error remain on the 3 first flowrate near the inlet (flowrate 1 with $196 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ of difference between model and in-situ measures, 2 with $164 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ of difference and 3 with $43 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ of difference) which are less sensitives to the optimization being upstream 3 of the 4 optimization area. The observed deviation for the other flow rates varies from 3 to $10 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The final bathymetry and differential between final minus initial bathymetries are shown in Fig. 8. The differences are small with a maximum increase of 1.3 m in area A and decrease of -3.4 m in area D.

Fig 6 -Field Coefficients

Fig 7 - Optimization loop

Fig 8 - Top : Final bathymetry obtained after optimization
Bottom : Differential between the final and the initial bathymetry

VI. CONCLUSION

This coupling method presented in this study between Telemac and OpenTURNS to optimize unknown bathymetry area significantly improves the flow rates on different profiles. The bathymetry is optimized to improve the flow rates but cannot be used to know the depth precisely in area without initials data, but only as a mean value. For this study, this assumption is acceptable as the breaches of navigation are located outside these optimized areas.

This work is still in progress, other outputs than the flows are considered to compute the error for optimization, like velocity and water depth.

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